

An Integrative Approach to Weather Analysis and Disaster Preparedness for 25 Districts in Sri Lanka: A Data Warehousing Perspective

J.M. Chan Sri
Manukalpa

Faculty of Science
University of Kelaniya

F. Shezreen Rathik

Faculty of Science
University of Kelaniya

O.D. Panaluwa

Faculty of Science
University of
Kelaniya

P.P.G.D. Asanka

Faculty of Science
University of Kelaniya

Abstract— This paper presents a unified method for weather prediction and involves data analysis methods, the OpenMeteo API, and machine learning algorithms like LinearRegression, AdaBoost and including XGBoost models for accurate weather predictions. This framework uses the OpenMeteo API and a data warehouse developed with the use of SSIS for data processing. Integrated with exploratory data analysis, the application of XGBoost and AdaBoost makes it easier to make accurate and detailed forecasts of the weather which in turn determines better decisions. The approach assists in attaining accurate prediction regarding the type of weather that is expected, hence enhancing decision making on weather in the 25 districts of Sri Lanka. Using actual meteorological data to test the system shows a marked increase in performance over existing methodologies to substantiate the system's worth. Due to the framework's flexibility and modularity, it can be incorporated with other forecasting systems while also being application specific, as necessary. Therefore, the main purpose of this research is to offer an integrative conceptualization of disaster risk preparedness and severity of weather conditions for Sri Lanka's 25 districts. Applying the concept of data warehouse along with machine learning model for prescriptive analysis, descriptive and predictive based on data related to past climate, socio-economic characteristics and geography of the region, the study constructs a framework to map the various risks and vulnerabilities. By integrating weather data, climate simulation, and all disaster risk reduction and response at the district level. The described framework ensures the proper accumulation of data, their storage, first analysis, assignment of appropriate machine learning algorithms, and, ultimately, the receipt of an accurate weather forecast. Precisely, it enables the provision of detailed understanding and trustworthy prognosis to help in improving decisions about weather conditions.

Keywords— Weather prediction, Classification, Forecasting SQL Server Integration Services (SSIS).

I. INTRODUCTION

This intends to transform how we choose and comprehend our destinations in a time when data influences our knowledge of the world. We examine the complex interaction between

weather patterns, climate resilience, and the optimal characteristics that make a site suited for different activities by utilizing big data, advanced meteorological research, and climate change projections. This creative strategy tackles the urgent need to adapt to and lessen the impact of climate change on our favorite destinations in addition to helping people make educated decisions about where to live and

II. DATA SOURCES

The Historical Weather API creates a complete record of historical weather conditions using a combination of weather station, aircraft, buoy, radar, and satellite observations. Reanalysis datasets are used. These databases close any gaps in meteorological data by estimating their values. In this way, reanalysis datasets can provide historical weather data for the open ocean and remote areas without weather stations. A 9 km spatial resolution allows the models to resolve details near beaches or in complicated terrain. At smaller scales, a higher spatial resolution provides more accurate weather data [7].

A. Use of Open-Meteo API

Open-Meteo is an open-source weather API that aggregates data from various weather stations, sensors, and meteorological sources. The API acts as an interface to access this collected weather data programmatically. Since Open-Meteo is an open-source platform, it adheres to the open data principles. It supports the notion of opening weather data to the public and promotes cooperation and creative applications of this data.

Variable	Unit	Description
weather_code	WMO code	A code representing the weather conditions
temperature_2m_mean	°C(°F)	Mean temperature at 2 meters above ground level
apparent_temperature_mean	°C(°F)	Mean apparent temperature, which considers factors like humidity.
precipitation_sum	mm	Total precipitation (including rain and showers)
rain_sum	mm	Sum of daily rain
precipitation_hours	hours	Duration of precipitation
wind_speed_10m_max	km/h (mph, m/s, knots)	Maximum wind speed at 10m above ground level on a day
wind_gusts_10m_max	km/h(mph, m/s, knots)	Maximum wind gusts at 10m above ground level on a day
wind_direction_10m_dominant	°	Dominant wind direction at 10m above ground level on a day
shortwave_radiation_sum	MJ/m ²	Sum of shortwave radiation
et0_fao_evapotranspiration	mm	Evapotranspiration calculated using the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) method.

The below listed daily parameters are used to accomplish our objective [1].

Table 1: Daily Parameters Used

III. Data Complexities

Data complexity of the domain is analysed through the popular 5Vs of data.

A. Volume

The dataset, which spans more than ten years (from January 1, 2004, to January 19, 2024) and includes a sizable number of meteorological observations, covers 25 major cities in Sri Lanka. With 183,006 rows and 13 columns, the dataset calls for powerful processing and storage resources, and big data technologies might be useful.

B. Velocity

The velocity is computed for both the aggregate dataset of 25 cities and for each city separately. The dataset is updated in real-time. Emergency response systems and other applications requiring real-time or near-real-time information are served by the frequent updates, which occur roughly every 48 hours for 25 cities.

C. Variety

The collection covers twenty-five different cities' worth of meteorological data, including temperature, humidity, wind speed, and rainfall. A distinct weather-related variable and weather 100 codes are shown in each column. The various kinds of data offer chances for sophisticated analytics and machine learning, enabling a thorough comprehension of weather trends.

D. Veracity

Pre-processing was done on the data to make sure it was clean and readable. Numerical columns either have non-negative values or missing values (NaN), and there are no duplicate rows or missing data. Additionally, the consistency and dependability of the data are enhanced by the lack of duplicates and missing values, which are essential for correct analysis.

E. Value

In our dataset, every numeric column has either missing values (NaN) or non-negative values. This result is positive, meaning that the provided numeric columns do not include any unexpected or incorrect negative values. This enhances the data's general consistency and dependability for any further investigation.

IV. RELATED WORK

Similar works provide an overview of existing research on weather prediction, specifically focusing on the impact of climate change and the utilization of big data analytics in the field. Researchers embarked on a study titled "An Integrative Approach to Weather Analysis and Disaster Preparedness for 25 Districts in Sri Lanka: A Data Warehousing Perspective" Before conducting their research, they extensively reviewed related works.

One significant work discussed is the research paper by Muthulakshmi and Baghavathi Priya in their research paper "A survey on weather forecasting to predict rainfall using big data analytics" [2]. The research explores the use of big data analytics in weather forecasting, specifically focusing on rainfall prediction. It addresses the scientific challenge of understanding atmospheric dynamics and the need for advanced methodologies for accurate rainfall predictions. Our study focuses on predicting 13 weather features, including mean temperature, precipitation sum, and wind speed. It also highlights the integration of advanced technologies like big data analytics. Both researches emphasize practical

applications in agriculture and disaster management. But our study provides specific insights into predicting multiple weather features across various sectors.

Another contribution to the literature comes from Vaishnavi P N, Rizwan M A and Dechakka M P conducted the research, "Big Data in Weather Forecasting," [3]. The study emphasizes the need for accumulating, assessing, and managing data, highlighting the impact of weather on various human activities like agriculture, power production, and pollution. The primary objective is to propose a sustainable solution to address the limitations of the existing weather monitoring system, especially considering global warming parameters. Also, the study mentions leveraging the MapReduce algorithm and the Hadoop database system. While our involves machine learning frameworks and the use of specific technological tools such as SSIS, Microsoft Analytical Services, SSMS, and Python for data retrieval, data warehousing, analysis, and visualization. Which focuses on disaster preparedness and weather analysis customized for Sri Lanka's 25 districts, utilizing spatial nuances and socio-economic parameters for comprehensive risk assessment.

The research, titled "Big Data Analytics in Weather Forecasting: A Systematic Review," [4]. Highlights the transformative potential of big data analytics in weather forecasting, highlighting its role in improving predictions and its significance in daily life. The study categorizes reviewed papers into technique-based, technology-based, and hybrid approaches, analyzing factors like accuracy, execution time and scalability. It highlights the historical evolution of weather forecasting from a human-intensive task to a computational process, the importance of big data analytics in overcoming challenges and emphasizing the complexity of weather patterns. Also discusses open issues and future trends in big data analytics.

The authors, Ria Jeby, Nishana Sageer, and Victor Johnson focuses on the scientific and technological challenges of weather forecasting globally. Discusses the importance of accurate weather prediction and the challenges it presents. It highlights the role of data mining in extracting patterns from large datasets, particularly in weather forecasting. The research proposes a system using data mining techniques to predict weather parameters like temperature, wind, and humidity, aiming to provide accessible information to users, especially farmers. Also discusses data preprocessing challenges and the application of artificial neural networks and empirical statistical techniques. Our study introduces a machine learning framework using boosting algorithms for weather forecasting instead of ANNs, validated using real meteorological data, that integrates data warehouse techniques for disaster preparedness in Sri Lanka's 25 districts. The framework integrates with existing forecasting systems and offers actionable insights for policymakers and local communities [5].

Another discusses the use of machine learning techniques to improve weather prediction accuracy, focusing on parameters like temperature, rainfall, and wind speed. It compares algorithms like Naive Bayes and Logistic Regression, emphasizing the importance of numerical weather prediction (NWP). The dataset used in the study spans from 1996-2016 for Delhi, India, and employs ANN and the Naive Bayes Algorithm. Our study also introduces a machine learning framework for weather forecasting, focusing on precision, reliability, and adaptability. It presents an integrative approach to weather analysis and disaster preparedness. The dataset used in the study spans from 2004-2024 for Sri Lanka's 25 districts.

The methodology involves using SSIS for ETL processes, Microsoft Analytical Services for creating multidimensional cubes, and Python for prescriptive and predictive analysis, including algorithms such as Linear Regression, Adaboost and XGBoost. Also includes a web interface for displaying analysis results [6].

There's another study that focuses specifically on enhancing flood predictions by improving the quality of data from EPS through a correction module. This paper presents a broader framework for weather forecasting and disaster preparedness customized for a specific geographical region. The proposed machine learning framework in our system is adaptable and scalable and integrates various analytical techniques to provide actionable insights for decision-makers and practitioners. Both studies share a common goal of improving the accuracy of weather-related predictions, albeit in different contexts [12].

Discusses the development of a weather prediction model for Sri Lanka using machine learning technology, specifically a multivariate Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM). The model accurately forecasts weather attributes like temperature and precipitation, identifying complex nonlinear patterns in past observational data. Our study introduces utilizing data warehouse techniques to construct a comprehensive understanding of vulnerabilities and climate risks. The methodology includes ETL processes, multidimensional cube creation, and time series prescriptive and predictive analysis using algorithms like Linear Regression, Adaboost and XGBoost. Despite their different scopes, both studies aim to use machine learning techniques for weather forecasting. [13].

Weather prediction algorithm for highway networks, combining CNN and LSTM to learn high-dimensional features from meteorological data and highway information. The algorithm emphasizes the importance of accurate weather prediction for highway safety and disaster prevention, especially in extreme weather conditions. Comparing this in our study. Various aspects of weather forecasting and disaster preparedness are measured by Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which are used to analyze extreme weather conditions [14].

V. REQUIREMENTS

A. Mean and Apparent Temporal Patterns: Apparent temperatures and mean vary due to factors like solar radiation, cloud cover, wind, humidity and speed. The Open-Meteo Weather API provides daily mean temperatures and other variables. Annual and monthly averages can be computed using Python by grouping data points by year and month.

$$T_{mean} = \frac{T_{min} + T_{max}}{2}$$

B. Identifying Instances of Extreme Weather Events

Stakeholders can protect people, infrastructure and property from extreme weather events by identifying them. Heatwaves can be caused by factors like lack of precipitation, dry air masses and clear skies. Heavy rain can be identified through data warehouse analysis and meteorological records, revealing clusters and regional patterns of anomalies.

C. Impact on Agriculture

Agricultural stakeholders in Sri Lanka can optimize water use, improve crop yield, and reduce water stress by combining data on reference evapotranspiration, and crop water requirements. Understanding the relationship between ET0 and agricultural water demand is crucial for agriculture, as it drives economic growth. Optimal growing conditions in Sri Lanka are linked to favourable weather, sunlight and soil moisture.

D. Wind Characteristics

Energy demand and weather variables

Long-term wind data from meteorological stations in Sri Lanka can reveal patterns and variances in dominant wind directions over various periods, seasonal, including monthly, and annual averages. This information provides crucial information about the climatology of wind patterns and their inter-annual variability. Identifying periods of high wind speed or gusts is crucial for determining high wind activity times and their consequences for coastal regions, infrastructure and agriculture. Understanding seasonal climatic trends and shifts in extreme weather events is essential for climate resilience, sustainable development and disaster risk reduction. Long-term trends in temperature or other weather variables may reflect natural variability and human-caused climate change. Robust analysis approaches and ongoing weather data monitoring can detect changes in extreme weather events over time. Sri Lanka's climate is influenced by temperature, wind speed, and energy demand, which are positively correlated. Predictive models using meteorological data can accurately estimate energy consumption patterns, enabling efficient energy management and planning. Historical patterns and machine learning methods, such as regression analysis and boosting algorithms, can improve temperature-based energy demand forecasts.

VI. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Warehouse Concept

A data warehouse is a comprehensive technology that allows critical personnel access to corporate information across an organization. It uses star and snowflake schemas, with the analytical framework for this study using star schema. Fact tables and dimension tables are used to analyze data, including weather code characteristics and city attributes. [9]

A set of comprehensive business information, such as weather code characteristics, city attributes, date attributes, and so forth, are encircled by numerous dimensions in a dimension table.

B. Data Set

The Open-Meteo API, an open source platform that makes meteorological data publicly available, provided the sample data set for the investigation. Mean temperature, apparent temperature, shortwave radiation sum, precipitation sum, rain sum, precipitation hours, wind speed, wind gust, wind direction, and evapotranspiration were among the larger scale data set components that were highlighted for analysis.

Using Streamlit, a user friendly web-based interface has been developed to collect the most pertinent data set from the open-meteo API for the designated areas. Additionally, this interface makes it possible to create a CSV file containing the pertinent data set, which can then be processed using the Colab IDE and libraries like pandas and numpy. There were workarounds for completing tasks including data purification, conversion, need-based filtering, sorting, combining, and aggregating, before the data was loaded into the data warehouse.

Figure 2: Data Set Retrieval

Figure 4: Date Hierarchy

C. Data Warehouse Design

The data warehouse design for this study uses the star schema, which comprises a single fact table encircled by many dimensions. Each fact refers to a single tuple with extra properties for each dimension. Dimension tables in the star schema do not connect with one another; instead, each dimension table joins with the fact table using a unique key known as a surrogate key (SK).

Typically, surrogate keys consist of integer values, with a distinct value supplied to every row. In the data warehouse, SKs will play a crucial role in protecting the data warehouse against unforeseen administrative changes, assisting with updates and inserts, and monitoring changes in dimensions.

SQL Server Management Studio (SSMS) was used to establish the database. To insert data into the newly created data warehouse, an ETL process is required. We utilized a Python script, with the help of the Pandas library, to perform this ETL task. All the data was then saved to a CSV file. Finally, a bulk query was used to load the data from the CSV file into the data warehouse using SQL Server Management Studio (SSMS) [8].

Additionally, this study utilized Type 1 SCDs for the majority of the dimensions related to SCDs.

The primary goal of this analytical method is to determine how climate change would affect ideal locations by meteorological analysis. As a result, the Fact_weather fact table includes four measurements: evapotranspiration, wind speed, wind gust, and direction.

D. Key Performance Indicators

We have established the key performance indicators (KPIs) shown below. By measuring these KPIs, we can keep an eye on system performance, spot areas for development, and make sure the system is meeting user needs such as Max temperature, Number of rain days, Landslide Occur and Cyclone.

Figure 3: Data Warehouse design – Weather Prediction

This study served as the basis for the design and referral of the data warehouse, which has three dimension tables and one fact table named "Fact_weather."

The dimensions Dim_weathercode, Dim_city, and Dim_date make up this data warehouse. The majority of data warehouses include date dimensions, which include the date hierarchy and other various properties, for functional and performance-related reasons. This specific date dimension includes the day, week of the month, quarter, month, and year [7].

Figure 6: Visualization of Key Performance Indicators

E. ETL (Extract, Transform, Load)

Data loading from source to destination is known as ETL. Extract, Transform, and Load are defined by ETL. We will be extracting data from a OLE DB source during this operation. Cleaning and modifications to the operational data are required to streamline the building summaries and prevent issues with impossibility, slowness, and security. These actions also help to prevent conflicts across source systems.

This study has just utilized ETL to retrieve data from Datawarehouse and load data to a flat file to do analysis. The insertion process was carried out by a separate technique that is covered in the VI-C section [10].

The ETL process for this study will be carried out using SQL Server Data Tools (SSDT).

Figure 7: ETL for Fact_Weather

This specific approach's ETL procedure is depicted in the above figure. After the fact table's whole load was completed by ETL, the "SQL Execution" job was run to perform truncation before loading the fact. By this point, the fact procedure and the cube dimension have also been completed. If the developer completes those things in the order listed, this will be a very convenient approach. Not every task needs to be completed by hand. To allow the SQL task for us, the administration only needs to upload the ETL package to the package store. That procedure will execute each time you've already scheduled it. In addition, it will have the capability to include the assignment of notifying the administration or users.

F. Analysis

The process of finding relevant information for business decision-making is called data analysis. This is done in order to extract meaningful information from the raw data and use it to inform daily decisions. That could change based on what each person or business requires. The majority of the time, analysis is predicated on making predictions about the future by examining data from the past or patterns that we have identified, such as predicting if and environmental conditions. Numerous techniques exist for analyzing data, including text analysis, statistical analysis, diagnostic analysis, predictive analysis, and prescriptive analysis [11].

Although data analysis tasks can be completed using a variety of tools, this study employed Microsoft SQL Server Analysis Services (SSAS) to provide our framework to users.

Predictive analysis

Weather forecasts for Multiple Parameters

The weather conditions are projected and presented in an easily comprehensible manner using Open-Meteo visualizations such as charts, graphs, and maps.

Figure 8: Weather Forecast for Multiple Parameters

To capture regional variances, suitable sampling meteorological data were gathered from numerous places within each district. The criteria for the projections are

provided for periods of three days, one month, three months, one year, and three years, per the applicable system.

Seasonal Forecast

Seasonal predictions in Open-Meteo estimate weather conditions over extended time horizons, usually spanning several months, by utilizing historical meteorological data, climatic patterns, and sophisticated modeling approaches. Because climate systems are complex, seasonal projections are often accompanied with uncertainty. By helping to quantify this uncertainty, predictive analytics enables decision-makers to comprehend the range of potential outcomes and make well-informed choices. Adaboost, XGBoost, and Linear Regression are some of the technologies that are utilized to analyze the annual average rainfall.

Figure 9: Seasonal Forecast

Performance Comparison Table

Model	Mean Squared Error (MSE)	R-squared (R2)	Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)	R - Score (R)	Optimal Hyperparameters
AdaBoost	0.910	0.679	0.954	0.824	n_estimators=1000 learning_rate=0.01
XGBoost	0.792	0.463	0.89	0.680	max_depth=10, learning_rate=0.01, n_estimators=1000, min_child_weight=2, subsample=0.5, colsample_bytree=0.5
Linear Regression	0.7898	0.459	0.889	0.677	N/A

Table 2: Performance Metrics for Each Machine Learning Model

According to the results of above Table 2 use of the XGBoost and AdaBoost models in weather forecasting is given in the following steps. This improved accuracy benefits various sectors, in agriculture through helping farmers make better decisions, in disaster through helping to prepare for extreme weather events, in the energy sector especially in the management of renewable resources, in public health by anticipating diseases outbreaks, and in transport to ensure safer routes for flying and sailing. The future studies should therefore be directed towards considering more sophisticated ML techniques like LSTMs, TCNs, Transformer models and a combination of all of them to increase prediction accuracy.

a. Prescriptive analytics

Prescriptive data analytics in Open-Meteo uses prediction-based recommendations to provide actionable insights based on weather forecasts. Techniques like Correlation Map, Bar Chart, Violin Plot, and Scatter Plot

help identify weather conditions, develop mitigation strategies and potential risks.

Figure 11: Violin Plot

Figure 12: Bar Chart

VII. CONCLUSION

In summary, the understanding, forecasting, and management of weather-related events in 25 distinct cities can be greatly aided by this climate prediction system. The system can produce precise forecasts by utilizing predictive analytics to examine past meteorological data, climatic trends, and other environmental elements. Stakeholders in a variety of industries, including disaster management, energy, transportation, and agriculture, can use these projections to reduce risks, maximize profits, and make well-informed decisions.

This is further enhanced by prescriptive data analytics, which provides insights based on predicted weather patterns. Prescriptive analytics assists stakeholders in proactively planning and implementing strategies to prevent disruptions and capitalize on opportunities by analyzing the possible implications of weather events and simulating various scenarios. By utilizing data analytics, we can create more resilient and sustainable communities that can withstand extreme weather events and changing weather patterns. We can also better manage risks and allocate resources.

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